

ISic0220

I.Sicily inscription 0220

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Termini Imerese, Museo Civico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Seppienae

2. Laidi

Apparatus

Text of ILTermini and photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175691

EDR 077923

EDCS 8900401

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques*

relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. At 1980.0523

Bivona, L. 1994. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del museo civico di Termini Imerese.
Kokalos Supplementi / Sikelika serie storica. Palermo / Rome. At 145

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